

NEWSLETTER

Allergy Cancer BioNano Research Centre

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October – December 2020

Welcome to our first ACBN Newsletter!

Dear Alumni,
you are reading the first Alumni Newsletter and if things work out, you can look forward to two such newsletters per year. We want to keep in touch with you, which is the point. We will include here information about recent developments, highlights from the research performed in ACBN, introductions to new groups and faculty members, and other items that may interest you.

In this edition you will find

- ❖ a **final report on the doctoral school ICA**, which is after 12 years now drawing to a close.
- ❖ news about the movements of our groups from the **Billrothstrasse to the NaWi** (a seemingly endless project that is now close to its finish) and
- ❖ an **introduction to the group of Angela Risch**, which some of you may not know yet

This newsletter
will appear
twice a year

Sad news

We are deeply mourning Anna-Maria Frischauf, who passed away on 9th of October 2020, in her 74th year. She was a founding member of ABCN and a longtime head of the Department of Molecular Biology. In her life as a scientist, she has made important contributions to molecular cancer research and has acted as an inspiring mentor of a generation of young scientists. She has substantially shaped the field of molecular biosciences in Salzburg and ACBN and has inspired us all with her positive spirit, knowledge, intelligence and gentleness. We shall sadly miss her advice and her personality. –

Univ.-Prof. i. R.
Dr. rer. nat.
Anna-Maria Frischauf

27th of Aug., 1947
9th of Oct., 2020

<https://www.forevermissed.com/annemarie-frischauf/about>

Biosciences and Health → ACBN

While science progresses, organizations change, which may be hoped to be the same thing. If you are a real long-time alumnus, you will be familiar with **Biosciences and Health**, which was the old name of **ACBN**. The ministry at some point wished a clearer indication of what we are actually doing, which prompted the name change to Allergy Cancer BioNano Research Centre (ACBN). On the one hand, this is just a different label for the same content. On the other hand, an institution like ours develops over time by development of disciplines and methods, as well as by changes of its members. Due to this, there may be another name change within the next few years; we are in discussion about that.

Playing the numbers game

Every five years or so, the Centre is undergoing an **evaluation** with external experts. In the first half of 2021, the next evaluation is coming up and we plan to make this a really useful event. Since 2019 we are in a process of strategy development that will result in a strategic plan for the development of the Centre, which we want to present to the evaluation committee. We hope for useful feedback, suggestions and corrections, so we can go into the future with a strong concept.

While we do not assume that numbers can sufficiently express scientific quality, we think that **numbers** are important. You can be a great scientist with five lifetime publications (Isaak Newton was, with five groundbreaking books to his name), but overall that is rare. Experimental science is expensive, so it is much dependent on budget numbers.

Playing the numbers game is part of science, so let us show some of ours:

Table 1:
Publication
activity

These numbers give only papers in which the PI is co-author, so the publication effort of most groups is actually higher.

PI	Total papers Google Scholar	Papers since 2013	h-index 1 Google Scholar	h-index 2 Publons ¹	Patents Pending and maintained
Aberger	74	37	36	31	1
Brandstetter	169	78	39	32	1
Cabrele	60	22	25	22	
Diwald	210	44	35	30	
Duschl	256	107	48	39	1
Ferreira	313	73	64	51	3
Gratz	59	22	17	15	1
Horejs-Höck	45	23	24	21	
Huber	300	51	52	43	
Hüsing	271	68	38	34	
Risch	217	59	53	42	
Wessler	126	56	34	30	

¹ Publons is successor of ResearchGate

January 2013 –
May 2020

Table 2:
Grant acquisition
activity of the groups

January 2013 –
May 2020

PI	Intern. Grants	Austrian Grants	Basic research grants	Applied Research grants	Total Grant Income 2013-2020
Aberger	3	8	7	4	4.030.000
Brandstetter	3	12	11	4	4.694.000
Cabrele	0	1	0	0	346.984
Diwald	3	2	5	0	1.060.000
Duschl	6	5	10	1	1.832.666
Ferreira	5	14	15	4	3.151.902
Gratz	4	4	7	1	3.047.000
Horejs-Höck	3	7	7	3	1.815.341
Huber	0	2	2	1	2.542.302
Hüsing	5	8	5	8	4.235.000
Risch	0	5	5	0	320.877
Wessler	2	4	6	1	1.682.000

Table 3:
Group members and
completed theses

January 2013 –
May 2020

PI	Group members Including the PI	Funded by grants	PhD theses finished Internal and external	Master theses finished Internal and external
Aberger	10	5	8	10
Brandstetter	28	24	10	9
Cabrele	6	1	3	2
Diwald	18	10	6	8
Duschl	21	15	9	10
Ferreira	15	7	16	11
Gratz	17	15	3	4
Horejs-Höck	10	8	5	17
Huber	17	6	12	11
Hüsing	18	8	12	11
Risch	7	2	3	8
Wessler	10	4	5	17

Albert Duschl

These are some of the numbers that we will take to the upcoming evaluation and in all false modesty, we think they are not bad.

I want to close with a final number, taken from the last report to the Rectorate. That report covered the period of January 2013 – November 2018. **During that time, 179 employed people worked within ACBN.** Of those, 140 were fully or part of the time employed with grant money acquired by the working groups within ACBN. Chances are good that you are one of them, either since 2013 or in one of the earlier periods. **You have contributed a great share to the success of ACBN!**

Well done!

All the best, *Albert Duschl*

Almost 12 years of “Immunity in Cancer and Allergy, ICA”, what an incredible journey

Success story

When I joined the University of Salzburg in March 2008, Albert, then Vice Rector of Research, informed me that a larger group of scientists of the ACBN Research Focus (called “Biosciences and Health” in those times) were successful in applying at the FWF for a doctorate program entitled “Immunity in Cancer and Allergy, ICA”. It was too late for me to join immediately, but Sepp Thalhamer gave me a chance three years later. Thus, after at least half a year of very intense and meticulous preparations of the whole group for the first interim evaluation in 2010, I, together with Silja Weßler was permitted to join the program.

What followed was an extremely friendly, collaborative, and scientifically productive period of attempts to solve challenging immunological questions by a very engaged group of colleagues at our Department. As a group, we survived two more interim evaluations, obtained mostly favorable reviewer feedback, extended the group of IA faculty members, and continued our passion for immunological research. Apart from numerous stand-alone follow-up projects, ICA was seminal for a significant number of other consortial grant applications, including several initiatives for Special Focus Areas, Research Groups, the Cancer Cluster Salzburg, and Christian Doppler Laboratories. Moreover, consortia have already been formed to apply for Doc.funds programs to continue the spirit of ICA in the high-quality education of doctoral students in cutting-edge scientific technologies to answer biological problems relevant in processes involving the immune system. ICA was and is a role model for many activities and routines for doctoral educations established today at the Department of Biosciences: structured application processes and hearings for doctoral positions, regular progress reports involving the cloud intelligence of the whole Department to support scientific interpretation and planning of experiments, the half yearly progress report symposium featuring renowned international scientists, and a number of social activities initiated to form a strong group of young scientists with a spirit of solidarity, especially promoted by Sepp. Unfortunately, the latter aspect had to suffer significantly due to the recent challenges of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic.

Group of ICA fellows of the third period, starting in 2015

ICA Symposium,
February 2020

Occupation (where known) of DK-ICA graduates following doctorate (N=41)

What we are most proud of is represented by the large group of alumni that participated in the program. Many of them spent significant time abroad in the laboratories of collaboration partners, thus widening their and our horizon of scientific tools and knowledge and forming a bridge to international contacts of our scientific community. They constitute an Armada of very well trained - both in theoretical and practical aspects - scientists, who spread the concepts of molecular biology research around the world, and who are also part of a network of PLUS graduates serving as contacts and supporters for the new generations of PhD students. Between 2008 and 2020, 49 ICA fellows graduated at PLUS. In the same time frame they published more than 180 peer-reviewed papers in scientific journals, which forms a large body of scientific heritage of ICA graduates. On average, about four papers were published per ICA student and almost one third was elaborated through collaboration of several ICA groups. After graduation, more than half of the graduates followed a scientific career, while the rest found interesting jobs in the pharma-/biotech-/food industry, in science communications and educations, as well as in public or regulatory agencies.

Christian Huber

We are happy to see this installment of Alumni Newsletters and hope it will become a forum for future exchange and contacts between all former fellows of ICA and the Department of Biosciences.

Christian Huber

Moving of the Life Sciences Labs from Billrothstraße to Hellbrunnerstraße

Say (nearly) goodbye to Billrothstraße

In 2015 the rectorate of the University had a very special Christmas present for the then Department Molecular Biology: The move of the Billrothstraße labs to the Hellbrunner Straße building, thus joining the Department within one building. The opportunity for the move resulted from the transfer of the CPM (Chemistry and Physics of Materials) Department to Itzling in February 2016. According to the initial plans, the move was scheduled for the summer of 2016.

However, this “big move” was postponed several times, and so we set up the Billroth Moving Lottery to guess on the true relocation date. Even the most outrageous bet turned out to be rather conservative but is nonetheless the truly deserved winner. Time passed as evidenced by numerous Billroth Oktoberfest and a barely single digit number of “Last-Christmas” parties.

Nevertheless, blowing up the temporal and pecuniary framework also brought benefits not only for the “evicted” groups, but also for the entire Department. It was recognized that geologists display cabinets are ill-suited for cell culture experiments and the general situation of BSL-2 facilities was acknowledged to be legally substandard and is therefore now modernized to the state of the art.

Not everyone was enthusiastic at the beginning and the bearer of evil tidings was unjustly blamed and threatened.

However, not long and - *sine ira et studio* - we solved our problems with tools and solvents at hand.

Meanwhile the labs are passing through the steps of evolution and will be finalized – well you won’t expect us to give a date now, right?

Still, a lot has been done and we are anxiously waiting for the actual house moving and enthusiastically looking forward to moving in into our brandnew labs. After years of waiting - the Berlin airport has opened by now – we expect to move in 2021 into renovated and significantly improved labs.

Gernot Posselt

Hans Brandstetter

Meet our
epigenetics
group

Of course, we were all hoping for a final Billrothstraße Oktoberfest and Christmas party in 2020, but an ugly virus again changed our plans. **It won't stop our Department unification.**

*“And so, heartened by their initial success, the desperate and reasonably violent wo*men of the Billrothstrasse battled on until, as the sun set slowly in the west, the outstanding returns on their bold science venture became apparent.”*

Hans Brandstetter und Gernot Posselt

The Cancer (Epi-)Genetics group

Moving from the German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ) in Heidelberg to join the PLUS, I – Angela Risch – founded the group in Oct 2014. We were very fortunate to join ACBN (then Biosciences and Health) in 2015, where we were most warmly welcomed. Within ACBN we are always pleased to collaborate e.g. by providing expertise on methylome analysis or in cancer related projects, e.g. with the group of Fritz Aberger. We conduct sequence specific analyses on our Pyromark and share an Illumina NEXTseq550 with the group of Richard Greil at the SCRI, which we use for genome-wide and targeted analyses. More recently, and with the help of our colleagues working in immunology, we are looking to elucidate epigenetic patterns relevant to tumor microenvironment interactions.

The
workgroup

Angela Risch

Florian Wolff

Angelika Heißl

It is worth mentioning that, while as a group we only joined ACBN in 2015, a number of individual group members have much longer associations with the Paris-Lodron-University and indirectly the Schwerpunkt ACBN – spot them below ...

Angela has a long-standing background in molecular genetic and epigenetic analyses in the context of carcinogenesis. She maintains her interest in genetic and epigenetic factors, and the mechanisms contributing to lung carcinogenesis within the International Lung cancer consortium (ILCCO, <https://ilcco.iarc.fr/>), and as an associated member of the German Centre for Lung Research (Deutsches Zentrum für Lungenforschung, DZL, <https://dzl.de/>), but is very pleased to have been able to contribute to projects related to breast and skin cancer since she has moved here.

Florian obtained his PhD as an ICA student in Annemarie Frischauf's group before joining Angela in 2014 as a senior scientist to build up the group. As part of our Cancer Cluster Salzburg (<https://www.cancercluster-salzburg.at/>) project he is interested in mechanistic aspects of hypomethylating therapy, and, more translationally, is conducting genome wide methylome analysis to elucidate whether methylation patterns may be useful to predict therapy response. Within ACBN this means we are benefitting from the analytical expertise in Christian Hubers group, co-culturing models in Jutta Horejs-Höck's group and cell culture know-how in Silja Wesslers group, as well as local cell sorting expertise.

Angelika has a BA in Molecular Biosciences from Salzburg, and an MA in Molecular Biology. Ever since her PhD in Linz and a stay at the Helmholtz Center Munich and the Penn State University, she has a special interest in ssDNA and non-B DNA structures in the human genome. She joined the group as a postdoc in 2019 and is investigating interrelationships between epigenetic marks and non-B DNA structures. We are very pleased that she has just won a starter grant from the Österreichische Diabetes Gesellschaft to investigate DNA secondary structures in the context of diabetes.

Esther Schamschula

Anna Strobl

Nicole Schreiner

Image references:

Paris-Lodron-
University of Salzburg,
Luigi Caputo,
Family A. Frischauf and
the articles' authors

Esther joined our group in May 2016 as a PhD Student within the doctoral school Immunity in Cancer and Allergy (ICA, <http://ica.sbg.ac.at/>). She started by analyzing genome-wide methylome data from twins (from a fruitful collaboration with B. Tümmler at the Medical University of Hannover), and became our pioneer for targeted sequencing. We are still putting the finishing touches to her project on inflammation related methylation changes in lung carcinogenesis, although after staying for an additional year as a Marie Andeßner-Stipendiatin, Esther has just moved on.

Anna studied Genetics in Salzburg and conducted her MA thesis in Sepp Thalhamer's lab, where she later worked as research technician. She joined our team in 2017 and has been supporting the team in everything practically, ranging from cell culture to pyrosequencing. She has made herself indispensable in keeping our equipment and supplies in perfect condition, and the recent challenge of conducting our lab practicals online has provided us with an opportunity to spot her previously hidden talent in producing videos.

We regularly host students, our most recent and truly dedicated MA student has been **Nicole** who also supports us as a lab assistant, and **Beate Buchegger** is our trusted tutor this term.

We are located in Billrothstraße, and yes, we will have to move (see pages 7ff). We are not particularly looking forward to the upheaval this will undoubtedly bring, but it will be great once we have relocated to the NaWi and will be able to interact even more closely with our colleagues there.

Angela Risch

With this, we conclude our first newsletter and look forward to the second one, which is scheduled for next spring. Visit us in Salzburg or online at <http://acbn.sbg.ac.at/>

***Have a peaceful Christmas time and
a Happy and Healthy New Year 2021!***